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DEVELOPMENT OF A SCIENTIFICALLY BASED FORMULATION AND TECHNOLOGY OF ENRICHED EXTRUDED POLYCEREAL (RICE, BUCKWHEAT, CORN) FUNCTIONAL PRODUCTS**Amantaev N.K.
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Abishev M.Zh.****Abstract**

The article discusses the development of a scientifically based formulation and technology of enriched extruded polycereal (rice, buckwheat, corn) functional products. For the production of functional food products, extrudates have been widely used, which are used according to certain principles. There are several methods of using extrudates for the production of functional food products. Thanks to the introduction of functional additives, products acquire new useful properties. Extrudates have great advantages in the production of functional products due to their enrichment with physiologically functional food ingredients. The use of extrudates for the production of functional food products makes it possible to obtain products with high nutritional value and good consumer properties.

Keywords: functional foods, extrudates, additives, composition, herbal powders, nutritional value.

Introduction.

Currently, the demand for new and healthy products has led to the development of a fairly successful market for whole grain, millet, and legume products. In this context, the unique nutritional profile of these grains, including dietary fiber, micronutrients, gluten-free proteins, and phytochemicals, deserves special attention in the development of new products [1].

Extrusion is a high-temperature, short-term processing technology in which food materials are plasticized and cooked through a combination of heat and mechanical shear under pressure. This leads to molecular transformation and chemical reactions that alter the functional properties, nutritional, and phytochemical composition of the food. The extruded product is stable, has a defined texture, and an extended shelf life, which increases its acceptability. Interest in the use of extrusion in the food industry stems from its ability to combine various ingredients into new products and, therefore, can be useful in the development of functional foods [2].

According to many scientists, extrusion is currently one of the most promising methods for creating combined products with maximum preservation of their biological and functional properties. The advantage of extrusion processing of food raw materials is the ability to perform dosing, mixing, grinding, structuring, cooking, and molding processes in a single unit, which undeniably reduces the cost of the resulting products. Extrusion processing ensures high sanitary and hygienic properties of the product: coliform bacteria, mold fungi, and salmonella are completely eliminated, significantly extending the shelf life of the finished product [3]. The aim of the current study was to develop nutritionally balanced extruded products with the addition of enriching additives from fruit, vegetable and berry powders (apple, carrot, beetroot, sea buckthorn and rose hips), as well as components of medicinal herbal complexes

(dried and crushed stevia leaves and Jerusalem artichoke powder) with minerals (calcium phosphate, iron sulfate and zinc oxide), as well as to study the influence of the mixture composition on the physicochemical and organoleptic characteristics of the extrudates.

Research Objects and Methods.

The study objects included plant-based raw materials: crushed rice according to GOST 6292-931, corn (GOST 6002-69) and rice (GOST 6292-70) grits, buckwheat groats (GOST 5550-74), fruit, vegetable, and berry powders (apple, carrot, beetroot, sea buckthorn, and rose hips), fruit, vegetable, and pumpkin powder, components of herbal medicinal complexes (dried and crushed stevia leaves and Jerusalem artichoke powder), components of herbal medicinal complexes (licorice and ginger root), mineral supplements (calcium phosphate, iron sulfate, and zinc oxide), and a mineral supplement (calcium carbonate and an iron amino acid complex). The research methods included the development of a scientifically based recipe, a technological scheme, the study of the organoleptic properties of the finished product, and the determination of the physicochemical indicators of product quality.

Results and discussion.

A mixture of whole-grain rice flour, corn, and buckwheat, enriched with fruit, vegetable, and berry powders (apple, carrot, beetroot, sea buckthorn, and rose hips), as well as components of herbal medicinal complexes (dried and crushed stevia leaves and Jerusalem artichoke powder) and minerals (calcium phosphate, ferrous sulfate, and zinc oxide), was prepared according to the following formula (Table 1). The resulting product was a polycereal mixture with enriching additives, possessing enhanced nutritional and biological value suitable for further extruded processing.

Table 1.

Formulation of a polycereal product with a highly prepared enriching additive.

№	Component name	Percentage ratio, %
1	Whole-ground rice flour	70
2	Whole-ground buckwheat flour	10
3	Whole-ground corn flour	10
Enriching supplement		
4	Fruit, vegetable, and berry powders (apple, carrot, beetroot, sea buckthorn, and rose hips)	7
5	Herbal medicinal complex components (dried and crushed stevia leaves and Jerusalem artichoke powder)	2,7
6	Mineral supplements (calcium phosphate, iron sulfate, and zinc oxide)	0,3
Total		100

The production process for new types of extruded poly-cereal food products with highly-prepared enriching additives involves the efficient implementation of the following processes: dosing, mixing, moistening, extruding, drying, packaging, packing, and warehousing of finished products.

A R3-KED-88 food extruder was used for the extrusion process. The extrusion parameters for the polycereal food product with enriching additives and the extruded food product with a functional enriching additive were: moisture content of the poly-cereal product with a functional enriching additive prior to extrusion was 25-28%, temperature was 55-65°C, and pressure was 0.1-0.12 MPa. When selecting raw materials for the production of extruded enriched polycereal (rice, buckwheat, and corn) functional products and an extruded food product with a functional enriching additive, we focused on the need to supplement the grain raw material with easily digestible lipids and amino acids: lysine and tryptophan, with a calculated amount of enriching additives (apple-carrot-beetroot, sea buckthorn, and rose hips) with increased nutritional and biological value, and auxiliary components (dried and crushed stevia leaves and Jerusalem artichoke powder) with minerals (calcium phosphate, ferrous sulfate, and zinc oxide). High protein (16 to 24%) and lipid (46 to 60%) contents were found in the studied raw materials, as well as carbohydrates (49 to 58%) in the grain raw material. The extruded polycereal food product with highly enriched additives, obtained under rational process parameters, was then analyzed for a range of parameters characterizing the consumer properties, nutritional value, and energy value of the finished product. The particles were crushed, sieved through a No. 025 metal mesh (GOST 4601-73), and analyzed. The extruded polycereal food product with highly enriched additives was analyzed for organoleptic properties according to GOST 15113.3-77, moisture according to GOST 15113.4-77, and acidity according to GOST 15113.5-77.

Organoleptic properties: the resulting product was granular, spherical, rounded in cross-section, with a rough surface and developed porosity. In terms of color (creamy with a brownish tint), taste, and aroma (corresponding to the original raw material with a distinct creamy flavor), the extrudate has satisfactory consumer properties, characteristic of a food product group known as extruded polycereal food products with highly prepared fortifying additives.

To assess the quality characteristics of the extruded polycereal food product with highly prepared fortifying additives, the following physicochemical properties were determined: swelling capacity - 3.1 g/g, solubility - 41.2%, and water-holding capacity of the ground extrudate - 4.55 g/g. These parameters were found to be consistent with those of traditional extruded products.

Other physicochemical characteristics (Table 2) also met standards for this product category. The energy value of the resulting product is 1356.7 kJ/100 g.

Determination of the biological value of the extrudates. The amino acid balance and biological value of the product were assessed using the following parameters: the coefficient of difference of the amino acid score (AASDC) and the biological value (BV) of food protein.

The experiment revealed that the mass fraction of amino acids in the extrudate exceeds their content compared to other types of grain crops. This is due to a decrease in the final moisture content of the extrudate and its partial enrichment with protein substances. A significant increase in essential amino acids such as isoleucine, lysine, and tryptophan is observed.

The addition of a fortifying plant-mineral supplement (PMA), characterized by a high content of vitamins and minerals, to the recipe mixture increases the nutritional and energy value of the finished extruded polycereal food product.

The biological value of the extruded polycereal food product with fortifying additives at a high degree of readiness was 87%.

Physicochemical properties of the extrudate.

Indicator name	Unit	Extrudate
Moisture	%	5,9
Acidity	degree	7,1
Bulk density	kg/m ³	246
Mechanical strength	N	1,41
Total sugar mass, DM	%	2,19
Fat mass, DM	%	2,85

Nutritional value analysis of the developed extruded product. One of the key requirements for food products, in addition to high consumer properties, is a balanced composition.

The ratio of components in the "ideal" product has been substantiated by the Kazakh Academy of Nutrition. Consuming 100 grams of the developed extruded product satisfies 29.7% of the daily protein requirement, 69.2% of carbohydrates, and 36% of minerals.

Conclusion

We obtained an extruded polycereal food product with enriching additives that is highly prepared and has good consumer properties and a sufficiently high biological and nutritional value. It has a more balanced composition of essential amino acids and is optimized according to the coefficient of difference in amino acid score (AASDC). We used widely available and inexpensive raw materials as the starting components of the mixture. We expanded the range of products manufactured by processing various raw materials with unstable

properties, and the finished product is classified as a healthy food product due to the use of a fortifying plant-mineral additive (PMA).

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